

1 Supplemental Figures and Tables:

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Supplemental Figure S1: RNA integrity evaluated in a 1% agarose bleach-gel (Aranda et al., 2012). Samples loaded in each lane: 1: 5570, 2: 5671, 3: 5841, 4: 6021, 5: 6097, 6: 6115, 7: 6227, 8: 5324, 9: 5633, 10: 6190, 11: 5656, 12: 5659, 13: 5701, 14: 6121 and 15: 6236. M: molecular weight marker from 8k to 100 bp. Presence of 28s and 18s ribosomal RNA (rRNA) intact bands (red and blue arrows respectively).

Supplemental Table S1. Anti-BLV ELISA percentage of reactivity (PR) at times T1 and T2 (N = 129 cows).

Sample ID	PR T1	PR T2
5028	121.1	184.0
5319	138.3	146.4
5324	79.6	59.5
5404	116.6	164.3
5423	128.5	145.1
5478	106.5	145.3
5482	150.2	179.9
5487	64.9	110.7
5495	102.0	152.2
5566	117.9	164.3
5567	95.8	210.4
5570	149.3	232.0
5633	66.8	52.3
5634	141.0	180.6
5638	106.3	156.2
5642	148.5	136.5
5644	139.8	148.9
5644	135.3	110.7
5649	113.5	116.4
5655	128.7	196.7
5656	81.6	37.9
5659	51.2	28.9
5669	76.1	83.1
5671	157.3	220.5
5701	64.3	56.0
5703	148.0	171.1
5705	131.1	171.3
5706	140.6	195.8
5709	153.0	234.0
5712	147.9	190.6
5718	149.9	193.1
5720	145.0	123.9
5730	127.2	176.8
5736	124.2	143.5
5743	158.7	140.9
5748	110.2	134.4
5749	137.4	155.6
5750	102.8	159.4
5801	118.4	187.1
5805	58.7	97.8
5807	124.2	124.4

5816	145.9	118.2
5819	114.3	104.2
5821	139.0	209.3
5822	143.9	194.4
5825	166.6	225.6
5827	106.0	125.7
5828	129.2	201.1
5830	15.4	6.4
5831	133.0	191.9
5834	129.2	203.1
5837	135.4	162.2
5841	166.3	239.6
5842	119.6	133.7
5844	150.3	233.1
5847	90.1	50.8
5853	92.6	130.1
5862	127.2	150.0
5871	90.2	142.2
5877	152.0	190.8
5879	167.2	185.3
5883	113.1	135.7
5888	137.8	123.8
5893	76.7	83.4
5952	154.5	208.9
5979	123.0	125.0
5981	97.3	124.4
5984	133.7	129.1
5985	145.1	136.5
5988	158.6	193.8
5989	62.4	72.8
5991	155.2	213.2
5992	46.8	32.6
5995	145.4	95.2
5999	164.7	149.9
6002	108.8	136.5
6003	170.6	204.0
6004	84.8	118.8
6006	79.4	28.0
6007	148.6	200.0
6014	150.7	200.9
6015	139.7	195.3
6017	48.9	163.2
6018	131.0	149.1
6019	93.5	86.9
6021	169.9	222.8

6022	106.8	68.5
6076	152.2	150.6
6080	138.3	119
6084	104.2	75.3
6085	61.5	35.0
6091	139.2	182.4
6093	118.8	173.6
6095	155.3	203.1
6097	162.6	218.3
6099	154.0	211.2
6106	140.2	205.1
6108	131.3	94.5
6109	171.0	204.5
6113	136.6	201.1
6115	161.7	228.4
6117	155.5	218.0
6120	75.0	82.8
6121	77.9	52.7
6122	135.5	195.5
6123	159.2	213.6
6179	32.7	12.6
6180	130.3	117.4
6190	81.3	59.1
6192	166.4	159.8
6195	115.5	95.6
6202	97.2	121.0
6203	135.2	155.6
6206	95.1	144.4
6208	103.5	151.6
6216	121.0	140.4
6227	155.3	232.3
6229	172.5	194.6
6236	47.0	44.9
6238	142.9	136.5
6239	97.3	119.7
6241	126.8	91.0
6244	147.3	159.3
6247	178.6	208.9
6248	114.9	118.6
6256	171.7	133.7
R762	156.3	88.2
R806	43.8	150.2
R864	145.8	154

Supplemental Table S2. Descriptive statistics for percentage (PR) of reactivity at T1 and T2

		PR T1	PR T2
Mean		122.7	146.3
Median		131.0	149.9
Standard deviation (s.d)		34.8	55.6
Quartile (Q)	1st*	15.4 - 102.8	6.4 - 118.2
	2nd	102.8 - 131.0	118.2 - 149.9
	3rd	131.0 - 148.6	149.9 - 194.4
	4th*	148.6 - 178.6	194.4 - 239.6

*Animals belonging to the extreme quartiles at T1 and T2 were selected

Supplemental Table S3. Log2-transformed gene expressions and cell counts data normality evaluation.

		Sample N=15		HPVL N=8		LPVL N=7	
		Normality	p-value ^a	Normality	p-value ^a	Normality	p-value ^a
Gene expression	<i>BoLA-DRB3</i>	yes	0.95	yes	0.34	yes	0.28
	<i>PRRC2A</i>	yes	0.06	yes	0.27	yes	0.46
	<i>TNF</i>	yes	0.22	yes	0.22	yes	0.38
	<i>BAG6</i>	yes	0.06	yes	0.12	yes	0.12
	<i>BoLA-A</i>	yes	0.91	yes	0.34	yes	0.28
	<i>LY6G5B</i>	yes	0.07	yes	0.32	no	0.02*
	<i>IER3</i>	yes	0.73	yes	0.98	yes	0.71
	<i>ABT1</i>	no	0.035*	no	0.02*	no	0.01*
Cell count	WBCs	yes	0.06	yes	0.19	yes	0.83
	L	yes	0.84	yes	0.54	yes	0.47
	N	yes	0.15	yes	0.42	yes	0.22
	E	yes	0.16	yes	0.38	yes	0.08
	M	yes	0.69	yes	0.80	yes	0.08

Abbreviations: WBCs = Whole blood cells; L = Lymphocytes; N = Neutrophils; E = Eosinophils; M = Monocytes.

^a Shapiro-Wilks test p-value at 5% significance level.

* Data whose normal distribution could not be assumed since its p-value was lower than 0.05 significance level.

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Supplemental Table S4. Whole blood cells (WBCs) and individuals immune cells population (N, E, L, and M) counts at T4 and T5.

Sample ID	Phenotype ^a	WBCs	N	T4			T5
				E	L	M	L
5570	HPVL	12600	2646	378	9324	252	5909
5671	HPVL	10920	3931	1420	5460	109	2488
5841	HPVL	9390	2347	1033	5822	188	640
6021*	HPVL	19390	2908	388	15706	388	13341
6097*	HPVL	18310	5127	549	11901	733	11580
6115	HPVL	11570	3008	1273	7173	116	6259
6227	HPVL	10210	2246	715	6943	306	9364
5324	LPVL	9500	4940	760	3420	380	3053
5633	LPVL	7780	2256	311	5057	156	3190
5656	LPVL	12240	4406	1225	6242	367	5643
5659	LPVL	7970	4304	877	2630	159	3604
5701	LPVL	8950	3043	985	4564	358	1948
6121	LPVL	10410	2186	1458	6558	208	4941
6190	LPVL	9230	4707	1015	3323	185	3596
6236	LPVL	10490	5979	839	3357	315	3460

Abbreviations: ID = Sample identification; HPVL = High proviral load; LPVL = Low proviral load; T = Sampling time; WBCs = Whole blood cells; L = Lymphocyte; N = Neutrophil; E = Eosinophil; M = Monocytes.

^a Cow phenotypic group assignment

* Animals with higher lymphocyte count than reference value at two successive samples (T4 and T5)

Supplemental Table S5. Percentage of reactivity (PR) values and proviral load (PVL) for cows sampled at T3 and T4 lactation stage (LS).

Sample	T1 (PR)	T2 (PR)	T3		T4 (LS)
			PR	PVL	
5324	79.6	59.5	83.3	< 10.0	Lactancy
5633	66.8	52.3	68.2	173.6	Lactancy
5656	81.6	37.9	74.5	0.0	Lactancy
5659	51.2	28.9	30.6	0.0	Lactancy
5701	64.3	56.0	72.2	0.0	Lactancy
5989 ^b	62.4	72.8	77.1	< 10.0	Dried
6085 ^b	61.5	35.0	63.0	0.0	Dried
6121	77.9	52.7	83.1	0.0	Lactancy
6190	81.3	59.1	39.4	86.9	Lactancy
6236	47.0	44.9	44.1	0.0	Lactancy
5570	149.3	232.0	204.6	30994.6	Lactancy
5671	157.3	220.5	190.8	26231.3	Lactancy
5709 ^b	153.0	234.0	203.8	127014.1	Dried
5825 ^a	166.6	225.6	182.1	1292.9	-
5841	166.3	239.6	211.5	33660.5	Lactancy
6021	169.9	222.8	196.8	17973.6	Lactancy
6097	162.6	218.3	210.7	79864.3	Lactancy
6115	161.7	228.4	189.3	110437.3	Lactancy
6117 ^b	155.5	218.0	201.4	62144.7	Dried
6227	155.3	232.3	192.1	186771.1	Lactancy

^a Animals with high PR but low PVL were excluded.

^b Not lactating animals at T4 were excluded.